

Effects of Increased RDC Injector Diodicity

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High-diodicity inlets seem like an ideal candidate for minimizing pressure losses during reactant injection in Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDC) while offering a higher resistance to backflow. In this study, the effect of a diode geometry in an RDC air injector is investigated experimentally and numerically. Different geometries based on the Tesla valve are implemented in the air injector and tested under non-reacting conditions. The effect of the diode geometry on pressure losses in both flow directions and on the diodicity is investigated. It is observed that the diode feature only minimally affects the forward pressure loss while showing an increased pressure loss for the reverse flow of up to approximately 45% at high mass fluxes. Key geometric parameters of the chosen diode geometry for increasing the diodicity are identified throughout this study. A parallel numerical study of a representative diode geometry offers insight on the flow structure for both flow directions. For the forward flow a pair of counter-rotating vortices is formed inside the diode feature while for the reverse flow a single vortex is formed.

I. Introduction

Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC) has the potential to unlock a step change in the performance of land-based and aviation gas turbines, as well as rocket motors. Contrary to deflagration combustion, which occurs at constant pressure, detonation combustion can increase the stagnation pressure of a system. One technology of particular interest in the field of PGC is the Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC). It operates by supporting a detonation wave that propagates around an annular combustion chamber. After a wave passes, the fuel and oxidizer are injected and mixed in the annulus prior to the arrival of the following wave.

Before RDCs can be implemented in practical systems, significant challenges must be overcome, particularly that of mitigating the pressure loss across the injector. Several experimental studies have investigated the performance of different RDC geometries, and although significant advances have been made in minimizing the total pressure loss of the system, no pressure gain has been directly measured [1]. Minimizing the pressure drop across the injectors has been identified as one of the main ways to achieve pressure gain in the RDC. However, pressure losses are in part necessary to prevent the backflow of reactants into the plenum and promote reactant mixing for stable RDC operation [2]. In addition, the injector system is strongly coupled to wave dynamics as the high pressure generated by the detonation wave front can temporarily stop the flow of fresh reactants and generate backflow of products into the plenum. These unsteady injector dynamics modify the reactant composition, thus affecting the detonation [3, 4].

Fluidic diode inlets in RDCs could be a good candidate towards reducing the coupling between the inlet and annulus. Introducing diodicity into the inlet could effectively allow for a decrease of the pressure loss in the forward direction while maintaining sufficient resistance in the backward direction, thus limiting backflow. Paxson et al. [5] performed a numerical study in which they found that the pressure gain measured from the Equivalent Available Pressure (EAP) increased with diodicity. The authors concluded that high-diodicity inlets are critical to achieving pressure gain in an air-breathing RDC. However, the simulations were performed in an idealized RDC setup where several loss mechanisms were not included and reactants premixed. In a numerical study, Keller et al. [6] found that including a diode feature in an impinging injector design significantly increases the injector diodicity. The diode feature was also conducive to a faster refill time for injectors with a lower stiffness. As stated by Kaemming and Paxson [7] increasing the injector area reduces the pressure loss from the injector (for a constant mass flow) and as shown by Bach et al. [8] an increased injector area also reduces the injector stiffness. Therefore an injector with increased diodicity could be useful in reducing

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the forward pressure losses while reducing the backflow of products into the supply plenum, thereby increasing the time available for the replenishing of reactants.

The objective of this study is to experimentally and numerically evaluate the impact of diodicity in the baseline RDC configuration and explore the diodicity in several candidate geometries. Seven Tesla valve-like geometries are implemented in an RDC air injector and tested under cold flow conditions. The effect of each geometric diode features on the flow is investigated at different flow conditions. A parallel numerical study is performed to provide additional insight into the flow structures inside the diode.

II. Methods

A. Experimental Setup

The RDC at TU Berlin uses a modular, radially inward injector design as depicted in Figure 1. In this study, the standard RDC geometry is modified by extending the combustor outerbody with a diameter of $D = 90$ mm to perform forward and reverse flow direction experiments. In the forward flow direction, the air is introduced radially-inward through a narrow slot at the bottom of the chamber annulus. The modular design allows for oxidizer slot heights of $g = 1$ mm or 2 mm. In the reverse flow direction, the air is introduced through injection ports located at the combustor exit wall. The air is stabilized in the extended combustor portion before entering the combustor annulus with a width of $\Delta = 7.6$ mm. The oxidizer exits through the standard injection ports used in the forward direction. In the present study, experiments are carried out under non-reacting flow conditions with compressed air. The diode features are cut azimuthally around the center of different fuel plates to modify the air injection geometry. The diodes are located at a nominal distance of $R = 45$ mm away from the center, which corresponds to the outer body radius.

The air mass flow rate is controlled by regulating the flow through a sonic nozzle upstream of the combustor. The static pressures inside the air injector plenum and in the extended annulus are measured with flush-mounted piezoresistive XTEL-190L(M) Kulite pressure sensors with an absolute pressure range of seven bar as shown in Figure 1. The pressure up- and down-stream of the diode feature is recorded for steady flows.

Fig. 1 Cross-sectional view of TU Berlin RDC setup with dummy fuel plate and diode feature.

B. Numerical Modeling

The geometry considered in this study is depicted schematically in Figure 2a. In the experiment, the diode feature is azimuthally cut around the center of the fuel plate. In the simulations, an axisymmetric converging-diverging channel of length 180 mm is used. The diode feature is revolved about a line of symmetry, which is parallel to the bulk flow direction in the channel. The throat of the channel, located downstream of the diode, has an area of 19.6 mm^2 for a radius of 2.5 mm. Although not depicted in Figure 2a, the channel is extended by a straight extension with a length of 60 mm on both sides to ensure that the flow is fully developed. Simulations are performed under non-reacting conditions with air as the medium. A perfect gas model is used, and the dynamic viscosity is calculated using Sutherland's law. In

the forward flow simulations, a total pressure is prescribed at the inlet boundary. In the reverse flow simulations, an average mass flux is prescribed at the inlet because a mass flux inlet condition in reverse flows is required since diodicity is only defined for flows with an equal mass flux. At the outlet of the channel, the flow is assumed to be at atmospheric conditions. A no-slip boundary condition was applied to the injector walls, which also assume no surface roughness.

Fig. 2 (a) Sketch of the numerical domain, straight extensions of the channel to the left and right are omitted for simplicity. (b) Detail view of the mesh showing all element types of the mixed mesh. Diode mesh with triangular elements on the left, mesh of the outer channel consisting of tetrahedral elements on the right.

The physical model described above is solved using Ansys FLUENT. The simulations use a density-based finite-volume solver. The Navier-Stokes equations are written in Favre-averaged form and are closed with the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model [9]. A production limiter is applied to account for the excessive production of turbulent kinetic energy in low ω regions [10]. The cell face interpolation for convective terms was implemented with a second-order upwind scheme and the gradients were computed using a cell-based least squares algorithm. The simulations were considered to be converged when the globally scaled residual values of the conserved variables had been reduced to at least $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ of their initial values.

The simulations are performed on a mixed element mesh, consisting of $\sim 10^5$ elements. The mesh features a refined region, as depicted in Figure 2b, with a maximum element edge length of $6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m near the diode. The overall minimum and maximum element sizes are 10^{-5} m and $1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m, respectively. It is observed that further refinement of the mesh does not change the macroscopic results significantly. Prismatic layers were used in wall-adjacent regions, giving near-wall grid resolution of the order of $y^+ \sim 1$.

III. Results

The objective of this work is to investigate the effects of introducing diode features in the air injector of an RDC. These results will be discussed in three sections. The first section will focus on a parametric analysis with the goal of selecting a feasible range of diodes and defining their geometric features. The second section will present the experimental results of non-reacting flow tests and the effect of the diode geometries and flow conditions will be evaluated and recommendations for promising diode features provided. The third section will discuss the results of a parallel numerical study to gain better insight into the internal flow structures of a representative diode geometry.

A. Determination of the Diode Geometries

A parametric analysis is performed in order to evaluate a feasible range of diode geometries to be tested in the combustor at TU Berlin. The baseline geometry, referred to as BSL for the remainder of the paper, is defined as the air gap without a diode feature. The diode geometry considered is based on a single fluidic Tesla diode [11]. The cross-sectional geometry of the diode features a spade-like shape as seen in Figure 3. In this study, a simplified diode geometry is chosen to reduce the parameter space. The shape of the diode is defined by the angle of the ramp section, α , the radius of the circular section, r , and the radial distance between the center of the circle and the start of the

ramp section, l . With the added constraint that the circular section of the diode and the ramp section must intersect tangentially, a diode feature is fully defined by α , r and l .

Fig. 3 Sketch of the diode feature geometry. Points at which the cross-sectional areas are important are marked and numbered in green (relative features not to scale).

Based on external geometric restrictions of the fuel plate such as the minimum wall thickness and attachment points to the RDC annulus, the boundaries of the parameter space can be defined. Within these limits, different combinations of r , l , and α are selected for the experimental investigation. This process is shown in Figure 4, in which the boundaries of the parameter space are plotted for two radii $r = 2\text{mm}$ and $r = 3\text{mm}$. The choice of radii is constrained by the tools available for the manufacturing of the circular shape. Based on the radius, the angle α and length l are selected to fit within the domain boundaries. The two angles, $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $\alpha = 35^\circ$, are selected because they are presumed to be sufficiently different from one another and are neither too small nor too large angles, however they are still initial guesses. The lengths for the variable, l , are chosen to span a large range of the parameter space within the boundaries. The final diode geometries are identified in the parameter space as shown in Figure 4. For each combination, other geometric parameters such as the angle β , height h , overall diode length L are calculated using trigonometric identities and reported in Table 1 for the selected geometries. It is assumed that these parameters can also impact the performance of the diode.

Fig. 4 Parameter space limitations and selected parameter combinations. The limits of the parameter space are described by the lines for a radius of $r = 2\text{ mm}$ (black), and of $r = 3\text{ mm}$ (blue). The markers represent the twelve selected geometries.

Number	Radius r [mm]	Angle α [°]	Length l [mm]	Height h [mm]	Length L [mm]	Angle β [°]	Volume V [$10^3 \cdot \text{mm}^3$]
1	2	20	6	0.06	8.0	88.4	3.067
2	2	20	9	1.15	10.6	54.9	6.542
3	2	20	11	1.88	11.7	20.3	9.454
4	3	20	9	0.08	12.0	88.4	7.243
5	3	20	11	0.81	13.9	74.2	10.629
6	3	20	14	1.90	16.3	50.6	16.84
7	3	35	9	2.64	10.4	28.3	13.743

Table 1 Geometric parameters of the selected diode geometries.

B. Experimental Results

1. Comparison to the Baseline Geometry

The effect on diodicity of introducing a diode in the air injector is assessed. The analysis is conducted on diode feature 2 from Table 1 with a radius of 2 mm, angle of 20° and length of 9 mm and is compared to the baseline case. The pressure losses in the forward and reverse flow direction at constant mass flow are reported in Figures 5(a) and (b) respectively. While the pressure losses in the forward direction for both the BSL and diode features are comparable, the reverse pressure losses are greater for the air injector with the diode feature than the baseline geometry. This effect is more pronounced in the 2 mm air injector gap configuration than in the 1 mm. From Equation 1, diodicity (Di) is defined as the ratio of the reverse to forward pressure loss at a given mass flow through the combustor annulus (station 3 according to Figure 3). From these pressure measurements, the configurations with the diode feature are expected to yield a higher diodicity than the baseline geometry across all mass fluxes considered as shown in Figure 6.

$$Di = \frac{\Delta p_{\text{reverse}}}{\Delta p_{\text{forward}}} \quad (1)$$

For both air slot heights, both the BSL and diode configurations show an interesting variation in the diodicity as a function of the mass flux, and it appears that this variation is correlated with the choking condition in the injector. In Fig. 6, the filled and unfilled markers correspond to the choked and unchoked conditions, respectively. For low mass flux, unchoked conditions, the measured diodicity is quite far from 1 and converges toward 1 rapidly with increasing mass flux, however some care should be taken in the interpretation of the low mass flux cases with the 2 mm air gap as the measurement uncertainty in the pressure measurement also increases. Beyond the point at which the flow chokes, the rate at which the diodicity converges toward 1 with increasing mass flux is reduced.

For the diode feature, both the 1 mm and 2 mm air injector gaps with the diode feature exhibited a diodicity value greater than one throughout the mass flux range (which corresponds to the typical air mass flux range for the operation of this RDC). In contrast, the baseline geometry has a diodicity less than 1 for both air gap heights over the entire range of mass fluxes, with the 2 mm gap height being significantly lower than the 1 mm injector. The larger error bars in the 2 mm injector case correspond to lower overall pressures at the sensor locations, however both installations appear to show an effect on the diodicity which is greater than the uncertainty in the measurement. Needless to say, this is an unexpected result and is generally considered to be undesirable for the operation of the RDC. These low diodicity values for the BSL injector could be expected to have a significant negative impact on the operability of this RDC and likely help explain the significant reduction in the operating range for steady single waves observed previously in this combustor [12, 13].

The slightly higher forward pressure loss (Fig. 5a) is most likely due to impingement of the jet exiting the injector on the center body. The sharp turn at the junction between the air gap and the combustor annulus is also expected to create separation bubbles that would also induce a forward pressure loss [14].

There is also a significant difference between the degree of diodicity for the 1 mm and 2 mm air gap installations for both configurations. This is likely attributable to the higher overall pressures in the 1 mm installation and corresponding lower flow momentum in the reverse flow condition, however this will be discussed later in more detail. In all cases, as the mass flux increases, and the extent to which the flow is choked increases, the diodicity values appear to converge to a steady value. Overall, the introduction of a diode feature in the air injector increases the diodicity without inducing a

major increase in the forward pressure loss. The impact of the diode feature is more pronounced at lower mass fluxes and for greater air injector slot heights.

Fig. 5 Pressure losses in (a) the forward and (b) the reverse direction versus mass flux for the baseline geometry and a diode feature geometry with $r = 2$ mm, $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $l = 9$ mm for a 1 mm and 2 mm injector air gap. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

Fig. 6 Diodicity versus mass flux for the baseline geometry and a diode feature geometry with $r = 2$ mm, $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $l = 9$ mm for a 1 mm and 2 mm injector air gap. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

2. Effect of primary geometric parameters

In this section, the effects on the flow of the length l , radius r , and angle α are evaluated. In Figures 7(a) and (b) the effect of the length l on the diodicity is investigated for diode geometries with a radius of $r = 2$ mm and $r = 3$ mm. It can be noted that for an air gap height of 1 mm, the diode features with an intermediate length l , namely $l = 9$ mm for $r = 2$ mm and $l = 11$ mm for $r = 3$ mm, have a higher diodicity at lower mass fluxes. For these diode geometries the angles are $\beta = 54.9^\circ$ and $\beta = 74.2^\circ$ respectively. These values of β are intermediate on the range of β 's considered and seem to induce a higher pressure loss in the reverse flow direction at lower mass fluxes. At higher mass fluxes for the 1 mm air gap, the diode feature with the longest length has the highest diodicity across both radii, while for the 2 mm air gap the intermediate length yields the highest diodicity. While no distinct trends are observed, the diode features with long and intermediate lengths perform on average better than those with the shortest lengths.

Figures 8(a) and (b) show the effects of varying the diode radius for different lengths for a 1 mm and 2 mm air gap respectively. It can be observed that across all mass fluxes for the 2 mm air slot and at lower mass fluxes for the 1 mm

Fig. 7 Effect of length on diodicity for geometries with (a) $r = 2$ mm and $\alpha = 20^\circ$, and (b) $r = 3$ mm and $\alpha = 20^\circ$.

air slot, there is a similar behavior: for a length of $l = 9$ mm the smaller radius $r = 2$ mm has a higher diodicity and for a length of $l = 11$ mm the larger radius $r = 3$ mm has a higher diodicity. With the diode geometry in Figure 3 in mind one can see that varying the radius mainly also impacts the angle β . Similarly to the length l , the radius r affects the diodicity measured. However, a direct trend between the length and the diodicity is difficult to establish, which suggests that other variables or geometric parameters might affect the flow field.

Fig. 8 Effect of the radius r on diodicity for (a) a 1 mm air gap and (b) 2 mm air gap across mass flux. The baseline geometries are plotted for reference. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

The impact of varying the angle α is considered in Figure 9 for a 1 mm and 2 mm air gap respectively. For high mass fluxes in the 1 mm air gap case ($J_3 > 125 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$) and across all mass fluxes in the 2 mm air gap case, the diode feature with an angle of $\alpha = 35^\circ$ outperforms the diode feature with angle $\alpha = 20^\circ$. Increasing the angle α could increase flow diversion away from the baseline path, inducing a higher pressure loss in the reverse direction and higher diodicity. The higher diodicity for the geometry with angle $\alpha = 35^\circ$ is most likely associated with the bias in inlet direction for flow entering the diode in the reverse case. As the air flows through a 90° bend from the annulus into the air slot, when the air turns, it flows directly into the diode sitting at the junction between the injector and annulus as shown in Figure 3. Keller et al. [6] observed a similar phenomenon in an impinging injector setup, where the impingement angle of the injector and associated bias in inlet flow direction for reverse flow affected the diodicity. It can also be observed that at lower mass fluxes, the diodicity for the geometry with $\alpha = 35^\circ$ for a 1 mm air gap decreases as previously observed with other geometries. Further experimental investigation of the flow structure for each diode geometry is required and is the topic of on-going research.

Fig. 9 Effect of angle α on diodicity for 1 mm and 2 mm air gap size. The baseline geometries are plotted for reference. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

3. Effect of the secondary geometric parameters

The impact of secondary geometric parameters, namely the angle β and the area ratio A_1/A_2 is also investigated. Figures 10(a) and (b) show the effect of varying the angle β on the diodicity across different mass fluxes for the 1 mm and 2 mm air gap respectively. Only mass fluxes at which flow choking occurs across the injector were considered to remove cases at very low mass fluxes for which a high uncertainty occurs. It can be observed that for the 2 mm air slot the highest diodicity is achieved for $\beta \approx 30^\circ$ across all mass fluxes. Such is the case for the 1 mm air slot at higher mass fluxes, however at lower mass fluxes, the highest diodicity occurs for $\beta \approx 75^\circ$. The angle β could affect the reverse flow redirection, which is likely responsible for the significant increase in pressure loss and thus an improvement in backflow resistance.

Fig. 10 Effect of the angle β on the diodicity for (a) a 1 mm air gap, and (b) a 2 mm air gap.

Figures 11(a) and (b) show the effect on the diodicity of the ratio between the areas defined at stations 1 and 2 as defined in Figure 3 for a 1 mm and 2 mm air slots. For the 2 mm air slot, the highest is generally measured for the greatest area ratio at $A_2/A_1 \approx 4.5$. This is also observed for higher mass fluxes in for the 1 mm air gap for $A_2/A_1 \approx 8$. A higher area ratio allows for a higher reverse flow expansion, which could increase the reverse pressure losses.

The experimental cold-flow testing reveals some key takeaways regarding the implementation of diodicity in RDC injection systems. Introducing a diode geometry in the air injector increases the reverse pressure loss and has a minimal impact on the forward pressure loss. Thus designing a high-diodicity injector system could reduce product backflow in RDCs. While it is difficult to establish a direct relationship between the geometric properties of the diode and its

Fig. 11 Effect of area ratio on diodicity for (a) a 1 mm air gap, and (b) a 2 mm air gap.

performance and more work needs to be done in order to identify the specific geometric dependencies, some observations could be made. Increasing the angle α could increase flow diversion away from the baseline path, inducing a higher pressure loss in the reverse direction and higher diodicity. In addition, the angle β could affect the reverse flow redirection, which is likely responsible for the significant increase in pressure loss and thus an improvement in backflow resistance. Furthermore, a higher area ratio across the diode induces a higher reverse flow expansion, which could increase the reverse pressure losses. However, these measurements are for a steady state in both the forward and reverse flow directions at the same mass flux which is not directly applicable during RDC operation. While this is helpful in selecting promising diode geometries for hot-fire tests there are expected to be additional unsteady and transient effects in combustion operation that are not captured in the current study. This therefore needs further investigation in the planned hot-fire tests with a diode geometry in the air injector.

C. Numerical results

In the following section, the numerical results for a steady, compressible flow through a fluidic diode are presented. The analysis aims to give insight into the main coherent flow structures present in an air slot with a representative diode geometry. The diode geometry chosen for this analysis corresponds to geometry 2 from Table 1 with $r = 2$ mm, $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $l = 9$ mm. The forward flow simulations were conducted over a range of total inlet pressures that span pressures from 110 kPa to 122 kPa. A corresponding reverse flow simulation was performed at the same average mass flux obtained in the forward flow simulation. The resulting simulated flow fields spanned the subsonic, transonic, and supersonic regimes. Notably, it can be observed that the highest Mach numbers reached in the reverse flow direction are on average 10% greater than those in the forward flow direction for the same mass flux. Figure 12 gives an overview of the simulations and the resulting maximum mach numbers.

Fig. 12 Maximum Mach number versus mass flux in the forward and reverse flow directions for a diode geometry with $r = 2$ mm, $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $l = 9$ mm. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

The streamlines for the forward and reverse flow directions for a forward total inlet pressure of 118 kPa are depicted in Figure 13 (a) and (b). A vortex pair is formed in the forward flow direction, while a single counter-clockwise rotating vortex is formed in the reverse one. The same flow structures were observed for the forward and reverse flow cases across all mass fluxes considered. In both flow directions, a stagnation point marked in Figure 13b, can be identified from the location of the maximum static pressure inside the diode. Interestingly, the deviation of the calculated location between all cases only amounts to 1% relative to the height of the diode.

Fig. 13 Streamlines colored by Mach number for (a) the forward flow direction at 118 kPa, and (b) the reverse flow direction corresponding to 118 kPa.

The Mach contours for different inlet conditions are depicted in Figure 14. In the forward direction, the fluidic diode appears to have a negligible effect on bulk flow in the air slot. On the other hand, in the reverse flow direction, the air tends to fill the diode's reservoir and is redirected around a sharp turn in the diode. In subsonic flow conditions, the reverse flow redirection is likely responsible for the pressure loss in the reverse flow direction. In supersonic flow conditions, the diodicity will be influenced by the additional pressure loss induced by the presence of a normal shock. It is likely that the significance of the shock-induced pressure loss grows when higher maximum mach numbers are reached. Indeed, Figure 15(a) shows that the forward and reverse flow pressure losses follow a similar, almost linear incline until the point where supersonic flow is reached at $p_t = 120$ kPa. The pressure losses are calculated using the area-averaged total pressures at the inlet and outlet. For even higher inlet pressures, the forward flow pressure drop starts to increase at a higher rate.

Fig. 14 Mach number contours showing the transition to supersonic flow and the development of normal shock at the channel throat at higher inlet pressures. Flow direction is left to right in all cases.

Fig. 15 (a) Pressure losses in forward and reverse flow. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively. (b) Diodicity as calculated from pressure losses.

The evolution of diodicity with respect to the mass flux, as given in Figure 15, reflects the trends of the pressure losses. A slight increase in diodicity up to approximately 1.2 can be observed, with the maximum value occurring at 116 kPa and 120 kPa. In the last simulated case, well into the supersonic regime for both flow directions, the diodicity decreases to a minimum value of 1.174.

It can also be observed that for supersonic flows, a normal shock wave appears directly downstream of the diode at the throat of the channel. Although the minimum area of the channel occurs directly upstream and downstream of the diode, the throat is located downstream of the diode due to the interaction with the expansion in the diode and the stagnation of the flow on the opposing wall. Upstream of the diode, the available area is only constricted by the turbulent boundary layer, which means that the available area at this position is effectively larger in both flow directions. In reverse flows, it is apparent that a significantly higher total inlet pressure is required to achieve the same mass flow rate as in corresponding forward flow cases. This indicates that a larger fraction of the throat area is blocked in reverse

flows compared to the forward direction. In order to quantify this effect, the effective area of the channel is calculated directly upstream and downstream of the diode. The effective area is defined as the area that would be required to reach the prescribed mass flow rate, given an ideal, unobstructed flow:

$$A_{e,rel} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho u} / A_g \quad (2)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, and u and ρ are the velocity and density at the center of the channel. The effective area is normalized by the geometric area, A_g . $A_{e,rel} = 1$ corresponds to an inviscid unobstructed flow and $A_{e,rel} = 0$ to a fully obstructed flow. The effective areas are calculated at the throat for the forward and reverse directions. Figure 16 confirms that the effective areas for the reverse flow direction are lower than the forward areas by on average 3%. This supports the notion of a partially blocked flow downstream of the diode. The figure also shows why the flow choking occurs downstream of the diode, as mentioned earlier.

Fig. 16 Effective area upstream and downstream of the diode. The effective area is normalized by the geometric area. Hollow and filled markers show unchoked and choked flow conditions, respectively.

Even though the diode parameters chosen for the simulations are also investigated in the experiments, the geometries of the two setups do differ significantly. In the experiment, the diode is cut azimuthally into the fuel plate, while the diode cutout in the simulation is revolved around the center axis of a channel with a circular cross-section. This leads to differences in the diode area and channel area, as well as the ratio of the two areas. Additionally, the experimental results are influenced by the flow turning occurring at the 90-degree bend between the air injector and the annulus, which is not present in the simulation. However, the numerical setup provides the benefit that simulation is conducted in 2D-axisymmetric geometry, which leads to lower computational cost than a full 3D simulation. Additionally, the simulation setup is relatively easy to replicate in an experiment. The simulation also provides an isolated, simplified view on the flow behavior on the diode, which is not possible in an experiment due to additional factors, such as flow turning. This allows for a more detailed analysis of the flow behavior on the diode. Lastly, it should be noted that transient phenomena, such as shock wave/boundary layer interactions, are not resolved in the steady simulations. Time-dependent variations of the location of shock, the strength of the shock, and the fluctuation of the boundary layer thickness are thus neglected.

IV. Conclusion

As seen in the experimental results, introducing a Tesla valve-like geometry in the RDC air injector increases the diodicity for almost all cases. Only in a few exceptions in the 1 mm air gap case does the diode geometry show a smaller diodicity than the baseline behavior. It was shown that the introduced geometry increases the reverse pressure loss while only having a minimal impact on the forward pressure loss. Therefore this geometry seems to be a good candidate to reduce reactant backflow while not negatively impacting the reactant injection. The effects of the design parameters of

the diode length l , radius r , and angle α , as well as derived geometric parameters such as the area ratio A_1/A_2 and the angle β on the diodicity have been investigated. While it is difficult to establish general trends of these parameters due to different behavior depending on the geometry, some observations could be made. It is notable that for the angle β the diodicity is lower at small and high angles and is higher in between. At higher mass fluxes, the diodicity also increases with the area ratio. The highest diodicity values however were observed by increasing the angle α from 20° to 35° . It is likely that due to the radially inward air injection, the turn in reverse flow path is utilized and the flow is diverted further away from the baseline path and therefore increases the diodicity. This highlights the importance of considering the base geometry of the combustor when designing fluidic diodes for the injector. It should be noted, that when looking at the diodicity and considering the pressure losses, a general idea of the behavior of a certain geometry can be established. However these are all considerations for a steady state in both forward and reverse flow at the same mass flow rate which is a simplification of the general RDC operation. While this is helpful in selecting promising diode geometries for hot-fire tests it is not intended to quantify the effects during operation. For instance, quantifying the injector blockage time or the ratio of total mass flow of reactants forward to products backwards during one period may be more suitable candidates than the steady diodicity. This however needs further investigation in the planned hot-fire tests with a diode geometry in the air injector. In the numerical analysis, a total of 14 forward and reverse flow simulations were carried out on a 2D-axisymmetric domain. The flow structure inside the diode was analyzed, where the nature of the recirculation in the diode volume and the location of the stagnation point were analyzed. It is found that a larger fraction of the throat area is blocked in reverse flows compared to the forward direction resulting in higher Mach numbers downstream of the diode. Further experimental validation of the numerical methods used in the simulation will be conducted in the future.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956803.

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